

Assessment of Knowledge on Swine Flu Among Adults

DINESH M.

Abstract:- The swine flu virus, sometimes known as the pork flu virus, is a human-transmitted virus that is endemic in pig herds. It is a member of the Orthomyxoviridae virus family. A survey of adult swine flu awareness was done in Navalur, Kanchipuram District, Tamilnadu, India. The goal of the study was to examine adult knowledge of swine flu and to link knowledge of swine flu with select demographic characteristics between the ages of 18 and 65. (18 years to 60 years). A total of 50 adults were included in the study. This study's tool was a structured questionnaire. It was discovered that 47 percent of people had insufficient understanding, whereas percent had moderately adequate knowledge. There is a substantial relationship between demographic factors, with a chi square value of 20.9862 ($P > 0.05$). S^* , We discovered that there is a lack of awareness among the adult population.

Keywords:- swine flu, knowledge, virus, adult disease.

I. INTRODUCTION

Swine influenza is a highly contagious acute respiratory disease that affects pigs and is caused by one of numerous swine influenza A strains. Pigs are infected with the virus through aerosols, direct and indirect contact, and asymptomatic carrier pigs. Incubation periods for influenza range from one to four days, with an average of two to three days. The symptoms of this form of virus includes sore throat, chills severe headache, coughing, weakness and general discomfort like those of influenza.

The swine flu can be diagnosed by symptoms of acute febrile respiratory illness, which can be verified in the lab by detecting antigens H1N1 influenza. Detection of a virus in real-time Culture or reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR). The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) reported two cases of human influenza A (H1N1) infection in April 2009, each with a unique mix of gene segments not previously seen in human influenza A virus. Additional instances were quickly confirmed, prompting the World Health Organization to declare a pandemic phase, indicating widespread human infection.

Swine flu spread swiftly over the world because to its

high human-to-human transmission rate and the high frequency of air travel. Swine flu cases in India reached 5-year highs in 2015, with over 18,000 cases and over 1000 deaths reported. Antiviral medications that target the early phases of infection, such as oseltamivir and zanamivir, are effective against swine flu. However, adamantanes such as amantadine and rimantadine are resistant to this strain.

A. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

- To assess the knowledge of adults about swine flu.
- To associate knowledge on swine flu with selected demographic variables.

B. INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Adults between the age of 18-60 years.
- Adults who are residing at Navallur.
- Adults who understand and speak Tamil-English language
- Adults who are present during the data collection

C. EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

The study excluded adult who were not willing to participate in the study.

D. HYPOTHESIS:

H1: There is no significant association between the knowledge levels of the adults on swine flu with selected demographic variables.

II. METHODS AND MATERIALS

The study was adopted to Quantitative research approach with descriptive research design and Purposive Sampling technique were used; the same size was 50. This study was conducted among 50 adults in selected area Navallur, at Kanchipuram district. Obtained consent from participants.

The data collection tool was

Part A: consist of demographic variables.

Part B: consist of Structured questionnaires was developed by investigator, to assess the knowledge on swine flu. Data was analyzed by descriptive and inferential statistics.

III. RESULT

Fig. 1: shows the distribution of level of knowledge on swine flu among adults. Among 50 adults, 47(94%) had inadequate knowledge,3(6%) had moderately adequate knowledge and 0(0%) having adequate knowledge about swine flu.

Demographical Variables	LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE						CHI SQUARE VALUE
	<50%		51-73%		>74%		
	NO.	%	NO	%	NO	%	
Age							
18-28yrs	8	16	2	4	0	0	X2=5.87055
29-38yrs	12	24	0	0	0	0	P=12.59
39-48yrs	19	38	0	0	0	0	NS*
49-60yrs	8	16	1	2	0	0	
Sex							X2=0.05909
Male	19	38	1	2	0	0	P=5.99
Female	28	56	2	4	0	0	NS*
Marital Status							X2=1.54077
Married	16	32	2	4	0	0	P=9.49
Unmarried	28	56	1	2	0	0	NS*
Divorce	3	6	0	0	0	0	
Educational Status							
Illiterate	11	22	0	0	0	0	X2=12.039
Primary School	17	34	0	0	0	0	P=12.59
High School	16	32	1	2	0	0	NS*
Graduate	3	6	2	4	0	0	
Income							X2=20.9862
5,000-10,000rs	30	60	0	0	0	0	P=12.59
10,000-15,000rs	8	16	0	0	0	0	S*
>15,000rs	0	0	1	2	0	0	
No Salary	9	18	2	4	0	0	
Type Of Family							X2=6.5071
Nuclear Family	15	30	3	6	5	10	P=5.99
Joint Family	25	50	0	0	2	4	NS*
Source Of Information							X2=2.3101
Media	15	30	1	2	2	4	P=12.59
Television	7	14	0	0	0	0	NS*
Newspaper	8	16	1	2	2	4	
Poster	11	22	1	2	2	4	

Table 1: Association of level of knowledge on swine flu among adults.

Table -1 shows that educational status and prior knowledge have a substantial relationship with knowledge

level. The chi square value obtained is 20.9862 ($P > 0.05$) S^* . Demographic characteristics are linked in a substantial way. We discovered that there is a lack of awareness among the adult population.

IV. DISCUSSION

This chapter discusses the findings of the data analysis in relation to the study's aims, Objectives and hypothesis. The issue at hand is research to determine the level of swine flu knowledge among people in Navalur.

The study was conducted using a descriptive research approach with a sample size of 50 people. The investigation was conducted on the Navallur adult population.

The first objective of the study was to assess the level of knowledge on swine flu among adults in Navalur.

In that 47(94%) had inadequate knowledge 3(6%) had moderate adequate knowledge and 0(0%) having adequate knowledge about swine flu.

The second objective of the study was to associate the level of knowledge on swine flu among adults population with their selected demographic variables.

Association between level of knowledge on swine flu among adults with their selected demographic variables was done using chi-square test the analysis revealed that education, income, has highly significant with the level of knowledge and other demographic variable were not statistically significant. so the research hypothesis stated that, "H1: significant association between demographic variable and the level of knowledge and regarding swine flu.

V. CONCLUSION

According to the findings of the study, information has an essential influence in community health. It is an appropriate approach of training for community health nurses to disseminate health information about swine flu warning signs, management, and prevention. To develop knowledge, educational activities are required. Improved information will lead to better practices, such as early detection of danger signs, commencement of appropriate treatment, and swine flu prevention.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- The study can be conducted on larger sample to generate the results.
- The study can be conducted among different groups like school teachers, home makers.
- A retrospective study can be conducted to identify the other strains of flu.
- A study can be conducted on the quality of life among the families of swine flu clients.
- A study can be conducted in different settings with similar settings.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Girish L. Dandagi and Sujata M. Byahatti. An insight into the swine-influenza A (H1N1) virus infection in humans. 2011 Jan-Mar; 28(1): 34–38.
- [2.] Ramandeep Singh Gambhir, Prabh Roonan Pannu, Tarun Nanda, Gagandeep Arora, and Amanpreet Kaur. Knowledge and Awareness Regarding Swine-Influenza A (H1N1) Virus Infection among Dental Professionals in India - A Systematic Review. 2016 Sep; 10(9): ZE10–ZE13.
- [3.] Ragasa S, Hirpa E. Review on Swine Flu and Status of Swine Flu in Ethiopia. Int J Vaccines Vaccin. 2017; 4(2): 00077.
- [4.] Megha kadam. A review article on swine flu. 2015; 05 (01): 12-16
- [5.] Shatavisa Mukherjee, Sukanta Sen, Prasanna C Nakate, Saibal Moitra. Management of swine flu (H1N1 Flu) outbreak and its treatment guidelines. 2015; 2(3): 71-78
- [6.] Manish sinha review of swine flu journal of infection and public health 2009 2 157-166.